

Profile of Testosterone Levels on Obesity in Its Relationship with Various Other Metabolic Syndrome (MS) Components in Adult Male Subjects

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ABSTRACT Testosterone is one of the hormones that play a role in metabolic diseases such as obesity. This hormone is associated with metabolic dysfunction, and low testosterone levels are associated with energy imbalances, impaired glucose control, reduced insulin sensitivity, and dyslipidemia. This study used a descriptive research design with a cross-sectional approach. Sampling was carried out by consecutive sampling in several health facilities in the city of Makassar from March 2018 to September 2018. As many as 62 adult male subjects aged 40-65 years were examined for testosterone levels in the morning that met the inclusion criteria and then analyzed using SPSS version 22 and values <0.05 were considered statistically significant. The research has been assessed as ethically feasible by the team of Health Research Ethics Commission of the Faculty of Medicine, Hasanuddin University. The average testosterone level was found to be lower in all components of MS. Testosterone levels in obese + 2-4 components (428,9) were significantly lower than in the reference group ($p < 0.05$). Testosterone levels in obese + 0 - 1 component subjects (386,9) were significantly lower than in the reference group ($p < 0,05$), testosterone levels in subjects non-obese + 2-4 components (454,8) were not significantly different from reference group ($p < 0.05$). This explains that obese subjects with an increasing number of MS components, the lower testosterone levels. In obese adult male subjects, testosterone levels are lower than non-obese subjects without being affected by the presence or absence of other MS components.

KEYWORDS Testosterone, Obesity, Metabolic Syndrome

Introduction

Testosterone levels are at a low limit before puberty and increase during puberty and reach the highest levels in the age group between 40 and 49 and gradually decrease with age [1]. Prevalence of low testosterone levels in men reaches 45% at the age of more

than 45 years and more than 60% at the age above 65 years [2].

Decreased testosterone levels can predict the incidence of central obesity and the development of MS in the next 7-10 years [3]. Mutual relations between testosterone and obesity can occur due to the accumulation of visceral fat, which causes increased secretion of proinflammatory cytokines, estradiol, insulin, and leptin. This mechanism inhibits the activity of the hypothalamic-pituitary-gonad at various levels. Insulin resistance also directly inhibits testosterone secretion in Leydig cells in men who do not suffer from obesity [4]. In other components of the MS epidemiological data have also shown that testosterone levels have a negative correlation with low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol and triglycerides, on the contrary, have a positive correlation with cholesterol-HDL [5]. In the blood pressure component, testosterone regulates cellular processes such as

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DOI:10.5455/IJMRCR.testosterone-obesity

First Received: April 22, 2019

Accepted: May 11, 2019

Associate Editor: Ivan Inkov (BG);

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phosphorylation of non-receptor protein kinases that mediate hypertrophy and contraction of blood vessels, causing hypertension [6]. In the blood sugar component, testosterone levels are positively correlated with insulin sensitivity, which is measured with hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic clamp [7].

In this study, the aim was to determine the profile of testosterone levels in obesity in relation to various other components of MS in adult male subjects.

Material and Methods

This study was an observational study with a cross-sectional study, conducted at various health facilities in Makassar, Indonesia, from March to September 2018. It has been approved by the ethics committee of the Faculty of Medicine with reference numbers: 58 / UN4.6.4.5.31 / PP36 / 2019.

a. Study population

Male subjects, aged 40-65 years, not taking anti-diabetic, anti-dyslipidemia, anti-hypertension drugs and at least stopping consumption of the drug for more than one month, outpatients, not appearing sick, and willing to take the study.

b. Data collection

Sampling was done by previously the subjects fasted 8-10 hours, then performed blood pressure examinations, waist circumference, fasting blood sugar, cholesterol-HDL, triglycerides and testosterone at 08.00 - 11.00 in the morning. Testosterone <300 mg / dl is considered low. The abnormalities of the examination results are included in the components of the MS according to the National Cholesterol Education 2005 modification Adult Treatment Panel III (NCEP ATP III) program and International Diabetes Federation (IDF) in 2005, including the obese component (waist circumference ≥ 90 cm), component of increased triglycerides (≥ 150 mg / dL), components of HDL cholesterol reduction (< 40 mg / dL), components of blood pressure increase ($\geq 130/85$ mmHg), and components of fasting blood sugar disorders (≥ 100 mg / dL). Then the subjects divided into four groups based on obesity and the number of components of MS. Group 1: Obese + 2-4 other MS components, Group 2: Non-obese + 2-4 other MS components, and group 3: Obese + 0 - 1 other MS components. Then compare each of the testosterone levels with Group 4: non-obese + 0 - 1 other MS components (reference group).

c. Statistical analysis

Data analysis was performed using SPSS version 22. Statistical analysis with descriptive statistical calculations, frequency distribution and Spearman's Correlation, Independent-t, and Chi-Square test statistics. The test results are significant if the value is $p < 0.05$.

Results

In table 1, the results of data analysis are shown based on the average testosterone level with the MS component, that the average testosterone level was found to be lower in hyperglycemia than normal (427.1 vs 456.9), low HDL-cholesterol compared to normal (441, 9 vs 445.1), high triglycerides compared to normal (425.1 vs 473.3), normal blood pressure compared to high blood pressure (414.2 vs 451.9), although each of these components was not statistically significant ($P > 0.005$). Testosterone levels were lower in obese subjects compared to non-obese subjects (422.8 vs 518.6), which were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). In the following table, one subject with extreme testosterone levels (> 1500 ng/dl) was excluded from the analysis.

In Table 2, the results of the analysis show that testosterone levels in obese + 2-4 components (428,9) were significantly lower than in the reference group ($p < 0.05$), Testosterone levels in obese subjects + 0 - 1 component (386, 9) significantly lower than in the reference group ($p < 0, 05$), and testosterone levels in non-obese + 2-4 components (454.8) subjects were not significantly different from the reference group ($p < 0.05$). Table 3 shows the results of the analysis of the proportion of subjects with low testosterone levels found to be higher in obese + 2-4 components of MS compared to non-obese + 2-4 components of MS (24.4% vs 14.3%). It was also found that testosterone levels were lower in non-obese + 0-1 components of MS compared to obese + 0-1 components (0.0% vs 14.3%). This explains that obese subjects with an increasing number of MS components, the lower testosterone levels. Likewise, in non-obese subjects without or with one component of MS, no testosterone levels were found.

Discussion

In this study, there was a significant relationship between low testosterone levels and increases in central obesity compared to other components of MS (Table 1). This is different from Grosman et al. (2014), who examined adult men aged 45-70 years with a total sample of 2096 was a significant relationship between MS. However, the research conducted by Blaya R, et al. (2016) conducted a study on 143 male subjects over 40 years, found a significant association between low testosterone levels and all components of MS except increased blood pressure [9]. Several studies related to other MS components showed a meaningful relationship of each component of MS with low testosterone levels [10], [11], [12]. This shows a large sample of the relationship between each component of MS with low testosterone levels. Based on data analysis, in the obese + 2-4 component group was the IDF MS criteria, while non-obese + 2-4 components were considered to represent the criteria of NCEP ATP III without obese. With the independent t-test, it was found that the obese group with or without other components was significantly compared to the reference group as well based on the prevalence of obese subjects + 0 - 1 component and obese + 2-4 components with lower testosterone levels than without obese (14, 3-24, 4% vs 0.0 - 14.3%) in table 3.

From this study shows that obesity is very influential compared to other components of MS against low levels of testosterone in MS patients. According to the search of researchers, the grouping of subjects like this has never been done before. However, several studies have shown that low serum testosterone predicts the development of central obesity and intra-abdominal fat accumulation [13]. This study supports the theory that men who are obese, adipose tissue is in an inflammatory state and is in a state of insulin resistance. This condition expresses the aromatase enzyme, which converts testosterone to estradiol. Increased estradiol concentration in adipose tissue provides negative feedback on the hypothalamic-pituitary axis, resulting in a decrease in the secretion of the gonadotropin hormone. The secretion of luteinizing hormone (LH) will also decrease, which eventually causes a decrease in steroidogenesis by Leydig cells. Central obesity is associated with an increase in adipokine, cytokines, and the production of other proinflammatory factors from adipocytes and macrophages, especially in visceral fat. These factors can change insulin response in the function of fat, liver, muscle, and endothelium which results in MS [14]. This study is different from the study by Alidu H, et al. (2017) in 132 diabetic adult men, it was found that total testosterone levels

Table 1 Relationship Between Testosterone Levels and Age and each Component of Metabolic Syndrome.

Component of MS		N	Mean	SD	P
Fasting Glucose	High	28	427,1	138,5	0,446
	Normal	33	456,9	161,9	
HDL Cholesterol	Low	25	445,1	159,0	0,938
	Normal	36	441,9	147,8	
Triglycerides	High	38	425,1	145,2	0,230
	Normal	23	473,3	159,3	
Blood Pressure	High	47	451,9	150,0	0,418
	Normal	14	414,2	156,9	
Waist Circumferences	Obese	48	422,8	142,9	0,042
	Non-obese	13	518,6	162,8	

Table 2 Testosterone Levels According to Obesity + Metabolic Syndrome Components

Group	Obesity + MS Components	n	Mean	SD	p
1	Obese + 2-4 Component	41	428,9	147,9	0,019
2	Non-obese +2-4 Component	7	454,8	108,0	0,132
3	Obese +0-1 Component	7	386,9	110,7	0,035
4	Non-obese +0-1 Components	6	593,0	193,1	Reference

Table 3 Relationship of Obesity + Components of Metabolic Syndrome with Testosterone.

Group	Obesity + MS Components	Testosterone		
		Low	Normal	Total
1	Obese + 2 - 4 Component	n	10	31
		%	24,4%	75,6%
2	Non Obese + 2 - 4 Component	n	1	6
		%	14,3%	85,7%
3	Obese + 0 - 1 Component	n	1	6
		%	14,3%	85,7%
4	Non obese + 0 - 1 Component	n	0	6
		%	0,0%	100,0%
Total		n	12	49
61		%	19,7%	80,3%
				100,0%

were lower in MS patients with the NCEP ATP III (2005) criteria compared with MS with IDF criteria. This difference is thought to be due to differences in sample size and the criteria of the MS used [15].

The conclusion in this study is that adult male subject's testosterone levels are lower in obese people compared to non-obese, without being influenced by the presence or absence of other components MS. The limitations of this study are the small number of samples that could affect the statistical results and also the presence of confounding factors such as smoking, alcohol, lifestyle, and diet that were not examined in the subjects. Therefore, it is recommended for clinicians to need to screen testosterone levels in obese adult men.

Competing Interests

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in this study.

Funding

All funds in this study were covered by the personal fund of the authors.

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